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ECONOMIC GROWTH, BUSINESS CIRCULATION AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ РОСТ, ДЕЛОВАЯ АКТИВНОСТЬ И ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ

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IQTISODIY O'SISH, BIZNES AYLANISHI VA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH

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This article provides information about the economic development of the country, the subordination of the development of the world economy as a whole to economic cycles, factors of the pace of economic growth, stages of the business cycle.

аннотация

В данной статье представлена информация об экономическом развитии страны, подчиненности развития мировой экономики в целом экономическим циклам, факторах темпов экономического роста, этапах делового цикла.

annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada mamlakatning iqtisodiy rivojlanishi, umuman jahon iqtisodiyoti rivojlanishining iqtisodiy sikllarga bo'ysunishi,

iqtisodiy o'sish sur'atlari omillari, biznes siklining bosqichlari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Keywords:

economy, economic crisis, economic growth, business cycle, economic cycle, national income, consumer basket, efficiency.

Ключевые слова:

экономика, экономический кризис, экономический рост, деловой цикл, экономический цикличность, национальный доход, потребительская корзина, эффективность.

Kalit so'zlar:

iqtisodiyot, iqtisodiy inqiroz, iqtisodiy o'sish, biznes tsikli, iqtisodiy tsikl, milliy daromad, iste'mol savati, samaradorlik.

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INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is a long-term increase in the real volume of gross domestic product, both in absolute values and per capita of the country.

The rate of economic growth is determined by the following factors:

- Natural resources;
- labor resources;

- type of socio-economic system and the state of the socio-political situation in the country;

- the composition of social production, its volume and quality, as well as the degree of organization;
- the degree of use of the progress of Science and technology in the production of the moment.

Two ways to achieve economic growth

Extensive method	Intensive method
<p>Increase GDP by expanding the scope of resource use (production includes resources that exist in the country but have not yet been used):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Increase in the number of machines. ❖ Hire additional workers. ❖ Keeping production technology unchanged. ❖ Increase of arable land. ❖ New Mining Development. 	<p>Increase GDP at the expense of qualitatively improving production factors and increasing their efficiency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Scientific and technical progress (NTP). ❖ Scale economies (increasing the volume of production increases its efficiency). ❖ Improving staff skills. ❖ Rational allocation of resources (the transition of capital and labor productivity from lower sectors to more efficient ones).

MAIN PART

Economic growth cannot be constant and uniform because it is subject to economic crises. Thus, the economic development of the country, the development of the world economy as a whole, is subject to economic cycles.

The economic cycle is the period of development of a market economy from one crisis to the second.

There are four stages of the business cycle:

1) crisis (recession) - the initial and determining stage of the cycle. Reduction of Real production, consumption, income and investment, growth of unemployment, exacerbation of socio-economic contradictions in society. The reduction in total production is called stagnation.

2) Depression (the lower part of the crisis) is an economic recession in an

economy that has become an elongated phase, the so – called economic stagnation. It appears after a crisis and can last for a long time. It is characterized by a low but stable level of production and a high level of unemployment (cyclical and stagnant).

3) recovery - gradual increase in production, additional workforce involvement in industry, profit of entrepreneurs and growth of population income.

4) the recovery period of the economy (peak) is a period characterized by almost complete employment of the active population, constant expansion of production of all goods and services, growth of income of entrepreneurs and residents, growth of gross national product.

The main stages of the cycle are crisis and recovery, intermediate phases are depression and recovery.

Economic development is the process by which an economy experiences not only growth stages, but also stages of decline, which can be accompanied by a relative and absolute decrease in the volume of production.

The main indicators of the level of economic development:

1) GDP and national income per capita.

2) production of the main types of products per capita (electricity, basic foodstuffs-cereals, milk, meat, sugar, potatoes, etc.

3) the sectoral structure of the national economy: the relationship between

large national economic sectors of material and intangible production.

4) the level and quality of life of the population (consumer basket analysis, subsistence minimum).

5) indicators of the economic efficiency of production.

National income is a newly created value for a certain period.

A consumer basket is a minimum set of food, non-food goods and services (utilities, transport, medicine) necessary to maintain human health and ensure its life.

Efficiency is the efficiency of a process described as the ratio of impact, outcome to cost.

A number of researchers argue that high growth rates do not lead to rapid improvements in the well-being of all segments of the population and are associated with a deterioration in environmental problems. They argue that the desire to increase production and consumption also leads to a deterioration in the personal characteristics of the population. At the same time, the distribution of the resulting wealth, which depends on the economic policy of the state, is an important issue. This determines how much accumulated wealth leads to an increase in well-being. The idea that a narrow focus on economic growth, its disregard for distributional consequences, leads to higher income levels and wealth inequality is becoming increasingly popular.

CONCLUSION

There is a certain contradiction between the pace of economic growth and improving its quality. At high growth rates, it can deteriorate qualitatively. However, low and even negative growth rates can be accompanied by increased consumer satisfaction as a result of the release of good products and services. Therefore, it is important to understand what the optimal growth rate should be in order to achieve high quality and ensure sustainable economic growth.

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